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Spatial modelling of *Xylella fastidiosa* distribution: two case studies in the Mediterranean Basin

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Xylella fastidiosa (*Xf*) is a phytopathogenic bacterium with a wide range of host plants, characterized by its genetic diversity. In this study, the effects of climatic and spatial factors on the distribution of *Xf* in two areas of the Mediterranean Basin were analyzed: Apulia (Italy) and Alicante (Spain). The pathogen was confined to the American continent and Taiwan, but in 2013 it was detected in Europe, in Apulia region, where extensive areas were affected by the olive quick decline syndrome, caused by *Xf* subsp. *pauca*. Almond leaf scorch, caused by *Xf* subsp. *multiplex*, was detected in 2017 in Alicante (Spain). Presence/absence data of *Xf* in the official surveys in both regions, Apulia and Alicante, were analyzed using a Bayesian approach through the Integrated Nested Laplace Approximation (INLA) methodology (Rue et al., 2009). Climatic covariates were obtained from the WorldClim database (Fick and Hijmans, 2017). In addition, a categorical variable was included according to Purcell's levels of disease severity based on minimum winter temperature from $< 1.1^{\circ}\text{C}$ to $> 4.5^{\circ}\text{C}$. These thresholds were defined in North America for Pierce's disease of grapevine, caused by *Xf* subsp. *fastidiosa*, and it is not known if those thresholds can be extrapolated to other *Xf* subspecies or geographic regions. Due to the different surveillance and sampling strategies carried out in the two study areas, the available georeferenced data presented a different structure. In Apulia, data were observed at continuous locations occurring within a defined spatial domain (geostatistical data). Therefore, the spatial effect was included using the Matérn covariance function, approximated as a solution to a Stochastic Partial Differential Equation (SPDE) (Lindgren et al., 2011). In Alicante, the samples were overlapped on a grid, so they were considered lattice data and the spatial effect was included through a conditional autoregressive structure (iCAR). Results showed that in Alicante the *Xf* was detected in all four Purcell's levels, illustrating the climatic adaptability of *Xf* subsp. *multiplex*. In Apulia, with much lower winter temperature variability than Alicante, only the high risk Purcell's class was observed. In both regions, the spatial structure had a strong influence in the models, but not the climatic covariates. In conclusion, disease spread was largely defined by the spatial relationship between geographic locations.

Keywords: Hierarchical Bayesian models, INLA, *Xylella fastidiosa*.

References

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